

π - π Charge Transfer Complexing in Diphenylamine and Benzophenone

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The charge transfer interactions including hydrogen bonding between diphenylamine and benzophenone studied by spectrophotometry are reported. In hexane Scott equation gives values of $K_c(400 \text{ nm}) = 2.30 \text{ M}^{-1}$, $K_c(390 \text{ nm}) = 2.12 \text{ M}^{-1}$ at $28^\circ \pm 1^\circ$; and $K_c(400 \text{ nm}) = 2.69 \text{ M}^{-1}$, $K_c(390 \text{ nm}) = 2.62 \text{ M}^{-1}$ at $18^\circ \pm 1^\circ$ suggesting better stability than for the mere contact type 1:1 complex and an absence of multiconfiguration. Complexing constants of diphenylamine- I_2 and benzophenone- I_2 systems indicate higher electron density in diphenylamine rings and π - π complex between largely planar electron rich π clouds of diphenylamine and electron deficient π -clouds of benzophenone, is postulated. Participation of hydrogen bonding forces is ruled out on the basis of concentration of the hydrogen bonded complex as determined by i.r. Thermodynamic constants have been determined and $-\Delta S^\circ$ values show that the donor and acceptor are subjected to more physical restraint when the bond between them becomes stronger. The likelihood of the participation of the complex in the photolysis of diphenylamine-benzophenone system is confirmed.

BONDING π to antibonding π donor acceptor and charge transfer complexes are formed between electron rich (Lewis bases) and electron deficient (Lewis acids) aromatic compounds¹⁻⁴. Powerful electronegative substituent groups somewhat deplete the π clouds because of inductive effects converting them into acceptors and numerous examples of NO_2 substituted acceptors are known⁵⁻⁷. On the other hand substituents like NH_2 having unshared electron pairs increase the π electron density of the rings by intramolecular donor action from the π island lone pair and aniline and substituted anilines do behave as donors⁸. The donor acceptor complexes further play a significant role as intermediates in chemical reactions⁹⁻¹¹. In the photolysis of diphenylamine (DPA) and benzophenone (BP) a reaction product, 4-(N-phenylamino)-phenyl-diphenyl methanol, which is not formed in less polar solvents like benzene, is produced in good yield in acetonitrile and tert. butanol¹² indicating a polar transition state. In view of the likelihood of a charge transfer complex playing a role in the reaction we have studied here the importance of DPA-BP complex in order to elucidate the mechanism.

The MO calculations based only on charge transfer well explained the long wavelength absorption of weak complexes, however, it is now increasingly realised that the forces other than the charge transfer render significant stability to the complexes. The weak π - π complexes appear to be stabilised by both charge transfer and electrostatic forces¹³. It is proposed to examine the share of different forces imparting stability to the complex.

The optical density measurements in the long wavelength absorption region of the complex have

been used to calculate the equilibrium constants (K_c) for the complexes¹⁴. The K_c values so determined depend upon the wavelength used and to some extent on the concentration of acceptors and donors. The wavelength and concentration dependence are apparently due to deviation from Lambert Beer Law^{15,16} and interactions between like and unlike molecules¹³ respectively. We have used spectrophotometric absorptions to monitor the complex keeping in view these shortcomings.

Experimental

BP and DPA, both Riedel grade, were purified by repeated crystallisation to sharp melting points of 49.0° and 52.5° respectively. Their uv spectra in hexane were identical with the reported spectra. *n*-hexane was BDH grade and was further purified by standard procedure and final fractional distillation carried out in high efficiency column.

Absorption spectra and optical densities (O.D.) were measured on a Hilger & Watts spectrophotometer using 1 cm quartz cells keeping solvent as reference. Infrared absorption spectra were recorded on a Beckman IR-20 spectrophotometer using 2 mm NaCl window cells with CCl_4 as reference. All measurements were made at $28^\circ \pm 1^\circ$.

Scott equation :

The following form of the equation was used :

$$[\text{DPA}][\text{BP}] \times 1/\text{O.D.} = 1/\epsilon[\text{DPA}] + 1/K_c$$

where ϵ is extinction co-efficient ($1 \text{ mole}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and l is path length (cm), concentrations in mole l^{-1} have been employed here.

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We have preferred Scott equation over Benesi-Hildebrand equation¹⁷ as in the former the points are weighted directly according to [DPA] instead of $1/[DPA]$ which has practical advantages. Results have been computed by least square method on a calculating machine. The graphs are least square plots. The determined values of K_c are for all the possible complexes, i.e. for complexes of various configurations having electronic transition in the visible region of the spectrum.

Results and Discussions

A more ratio plot vs optical density showed the formation of 1 : 1 complex in accordance with earlier observations¹⁸. A spectrum of a solution of DPA (0.12M) and BP (0.008M) in *n*-hexane is given in Fig. 1. DPA does not absorb in this region and for

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra in *n*-hexane. I: benzophenone (0.008M); II: diphenylamine (0.12M) + benzophenone (0.008M).

reference the spectrum of BP (0.008M) is shown. No maximum is observed. These types of spectra have been observed in contact charge transfer complexes^{4,19-21} which are weak due to shift of the electron density from bonding to antibonding orbitals. In DPA the intramolecular donor action from the lone pair of nitrogen increases the electron density in the rings (DPA is largely planar²²) whereas CO group in BP draws the electron cloud (induction effect) leaving the pi rings electron deficient and this is expected to lead to a weak DPA-BP complex. However, the K_c values (cf. Table 1) are high indicating better stability than that for a contact charge transfer complex. It is known that forces other than charge transfer (including van der Waals type) can bind the complexes and in the present case hydrogen bonding, a donor acceptor complexing, could be responsible for extra stability. The i.r. spectrum of DPA (0.12M) and BP (0.11M) in carbon tetrachloride showed two peaks of NH stretching at 3460 cm^{-1} and at 3420 cm^{-1} in a high resolution scan. The observed shift of 40 cm^{-1} due to hydrogen bonding is equivalent to weakening of NH bond to its 97.7% strength and hydrogen bond of 2.2 kcal

mole⁻¹ (NH bond = $96.6\text{ kcal mole}^{-1}$) (ref. 23). The calculations based on peak heights of NH and NH-OC groups stretchings give an optimum value of $[DPA\cdot BP]/[DPA] = 5.6 \times 10^{-2}$ which when compared with the value of 2.9×10^{-2} obtained from K_c (cf. Table 1) shows that hydrogen bonding has no contribution in charge transfer complexing.

TABLE I—THERMODYNAMIC CONSTANTS FOR DPA-BP COMPLEX IN *n*-HEXANE

Temp. °C	K_c M ⁻¹	$-\Delta F^\circ$ K.cal.mole ⁻¹	$-\Delta S^\circ$ cal.mole ⁻¹ deg ⁻¹	$-\Delta H^\circ$ K.cal.mole ⁻¹
28±1	2.12 2.30	0.20	9.77	3.15
18±1	2.62 2.69	0.24	9.98	—

Note: The values of ΔF° , ΔS° , and ΔH° have been calculated from the mean values of $K_c = 2.21\text{ M}^{-1}$ at $28 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ and $K_c = 2.65\text{ M}^{-1}$ at $18 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$.

Scott equation²⁴ least square plots, $[BP][DPA]/\text{O.D.}$ vs $[DPA]$, are given in Figs. 2 and 3. It has been shown that the photometric estimation of the concentration of the complex at wavelengths other than its maximum is possible¹⁴ and all our measurements are at 390 or 400 nm. At 400 nm corrections due to uncomplexed components are negligible. At 390 nm corrections due to uncomplexed BP was calculated by using the value of K_c at 400 nm. The different K_c 's at different wavelengths have been attributed to Lambert-Beer law being not obeyed and as the K_c 's here are same at 390 and 400 nm, K_c (400 nm) = 2.30 M^{-1} , K_c (390 nm) = 2.12 M^{-1} at $28 \pm 1^\circ$, K_c (400 nm) = 2.69 M^{-1} , K_c (390 nm) = 2.62 M^{-1} at $18 \pm 1^\circ$, it appears the law is obeyed here within the experimental error.

Fig. 2. Scott plot for the benzophenone system in *n*-hexane at $18 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ ⊙-⊙ absorbance at 400 nm; O-O absorbance at 390 nm. Concentration of benzophenone varies from $0.25 \times 10^{-2}\text{ M}$ to $0.72 \times 10^{-2}\text{ M}$ and diphenylamine from $17.6 \times 10^{-2}\text{ M}$ to $12.8 \times 10^{-2}\text{ M}$

Fig. 3. Plot for the benzophenone diphenylamine system in n-hexane at $28 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$. $\odot$ - $\odot$ absorbance at 400 nm; $\square$ - $\square$ absorbance at 390 nm. Concentration of benzophenone varies from $.25 \times 10^{-2}M$ to $.64 \times 10^{-2}M$ and of diphenylamine from $17.6 \times 10^{-2}M$ to $13.6 \times 10^{-2}M$.

We examined K_c 's for DPA- I_2 and BP- I_2 systems in methanol and carbon tetrachloride to determine the relative electron density in pi clouds of DPA and BP. A dark chemical reaction occurred in DPA- I_2 system in methanol which did not permit the evaluation of K_c . In carbon tetrachloride the values are $1.0 M^{-1}$ and $1.5 M^{-1}$ for DPA and BP respectively. A difference in electron density in DPA and BP rings is indicated but it can not be a quantitative measure for the complexing as the complexes, formed with I_2 are pi-sigma type.

The thermodynamic constants are reported in Table 1. The values of $-\Delta S^\circ$ show that the donor and acceptor are subjected to more physical restraint as the bond between them becomes stronger. However, it is difficult to precisely attribute the lower stability at higher temperature but the trend is similar to the one observed by other workers^{16, 25}.

In the system BP (0.11 M) sensitized photolysis of DPA (0.12 M) giving 4-(N-phenylamino)-phenyl-diphenyl methanol, the concentration of the complex is expected to be less in solvents forming hydrogen

bonds with BP and greater than 2.9×10^{-2} in polar solvents. In view of low quantum yield it is therefore, quite likely that the product is formed through the excited charge transfer complex ($\epsilon_{\text{complex}} > \epsilon_{\text{DPA}}$) which has higher stability in polar solvents.

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